

THE MAIN APPROACHES OF ORGANIZING MULTIMEDIA EDUCATION FOR PRIMARY CLASSES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

Sarviniso Sanakulova

PhD student of Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after
K.Niyazi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8044518>

Abstract. *A surge of interest has been seen in the use of multimedia in educational computer applications. Some researchers examine which particular benefits media provide for students' learning. This article deals the issue of techniques for the effective use of multimedia in improving the quality and effectiveness of primary classes, the benefits and problems of integrating science content with multimedia design. Primary education is carried out with the wide and effective use of multimedia, active teaching methods and gaming technologies that can develop students' ability of active, logical and critical thinking.*

Keywords: *primary education, efficiency, multimedia, develop ability, logical thinking, learning styles, curriculum, complexity, versatility.*

At present, much attention is paid to the use of multimedia in teaching foreign languages, especially to young learners, in accordance with the specifics of their age and special ability to perceive educational material. Pedagogical systems and educational technologies, in particular multimedia, attract great attention of teachers as well in order to improve the education of young learners.

Multimedia is often applied to many courses as it provides a wide diversity of learning styles and modalities. Learning style is the term that relates to characteristic cognitive behaviour and helps in defining how learners perceive, interact with, and respond to learning setting. It is proved that learners are more comfortable with gaining knowledge in the environment which is connected to their predominant learning style. Each student in the classroom has a preferred learning modality as visual, aural, and kinesthetic. Some learners are multimodal which is the combination of all mentioned above modalities. Multimedia helps in establishing curriculum that appeals to visual, aural and kinesthetic students, therefore, learners have equal opportunities in their performances. Students are encouraged to develop a versatile approach to learning by presented material in a diversity of modes.

In the concept of "Development of the public education system until 2030" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019, priorities such as "taking measures to systematically organize the process of developing and using multimedia products in education" are defined. This, in turn, requires the improvement of the methodology of effective use of multimedia programs in the educational process.[1]

The learning system is the basic category of pedagogical science, namely teaching methods. It consists of many different elements (subsystems), such as goals, objectives, content, process, methods, principles, organizational forms and teaching aids. All these elements contribute to the solution of a single task of the system - teaching a foreign language to young learners.

The complexity of any system is determined by the amount of information contained in it. The more information a system contains, the more difficult it is to understand. The experience of many developers dealing with systems characterized by complexity, versatility and variety of

elements convinces us that the traditional approach to teaching young learners, based on the allocation of subsystems or elements independently studied and designed within the framework of the corresponding special disciplines, gives rise to numerous and intractable problems.

All this equally applies to the methodology of teaching foreign languages to young learners, using the knowledge of linguistics, physiology, pedagogy, psychology and other sciences.

Every year, the process of saturation of educational institutions with digital technology is not only enhanced, but also improved.

It is possible to evaluate the innovative processes taking place in the education system in different ways. One of them is the natural desire of innovative teachers to find, with the help of new technology, answers to unsolved problems of pedagogy, methods of teaching a foreign language to young learners, so we need to determine the role and place of multimedia teaching software in the organization of teaching English to young learners.

The creation of multimedia products has become much easier with the advent of specialized programs that allow:

1. Work with sound, as well as with sound files created in other specialized programs.
2. Work with graphic video images.
3. Arrange sound, graphic and video components.
4. Provide user interaction and programming in an embedded language and much more.

There are two ways to use multimedia learning software in elementary school when teaching a foreign language:

1. multimedia teaching software is a tool for expressing exactly how teachers would like to see themselves.
2. Multimedia learning software is being used as an aid to change learning strategies for younger students.

These paths, initially unconscious by teachers, were revealed [150 p. 5] as a result of analyzing how they use new information technologies. In the first case, we are dealing with a "catalyst" for the process of change in education, and in the second case, with technology to support learning.

The ability to work with multimedia in the classroom is growing faster than our understanding of new pedagogical, methodological and didactic problems associated with the informatization of society. Therefore, it is necessary to comprehend, analyze and systematize the accumulated experience of using multimedia teaching software in the educational process, especially in the study of foreign languages by first-graders.

As noted above, this scientific direction in pedagogy has emerged quite recently, and therefore some of its basic concepts and definitions need to be clarified. The main terms and their meanings are:

Multimedia (multifunctional) The term "media" comes from the Latin media "environment, or information carrier". "Multimedia" means the ability to work with information in various forms, and not only in digital form, like ordinary computers, first of all, there is sound and video information. Multimedia language learning programs use various methodological techniques that allow for familiarization, training and control. [47 p. 3]

With the help of multimedia programs, you can learn a foreign language at an individual pace and sequence, which allows you to take into account the psychological characteristics of each student of primary classes. In addition, the effectiveness of learning increases due to the fact that

students receive all kinds of information (graphically, sound) at the moment when they need it, they can return at any time and repeat what they have previously learned and ask the multimedia program for a hint, which is the feedback. .

Multimedia learning software:

1. The carrier of the subject content of education, as well as the types of activities defined by the program for compulsory assimilation, taking into account the age characteristics of primary school students.

2. A multimedia manual is not only an important but also an entertaining source of knowledge for primary school students.

On the one hand, a multimedia manual is a source of knowledge, a carrier of the content of education, as well as the types of activities to be mastered. On the other hand, the multimedia manual is a learning tool. And as a means of teaching, a multimedia manual has a well-defined material form, which, to a much greater extent than a book, is related to the content, the process of assimilation of this content, the result of assimilation of information by young learners.

The use of multimedia learning software is also a factor that positively affects the motivation to learn a language. A positive atmosphere in the classroom and the interest of students in the subject of study are of great importance. Particular attention should be paid to determining the role and place of multimedia software in the learning process. Multimedia learning uses the unique possibilities of new technologies in addition to traditional learning and only when it is appropriate.

Despite the potentially high efficiency of modern educational multimedia programs, the learning outcomes in most cases do not meet expectations. Many methodologists attribute the failure of multimedia learning to the fact that many programs are weak from a methodological point of view, do not meet the learning objectives, have significant limitations and cannot compete with traditional learning technologies. However, the main problem is not in the shortcomings of the new tools, but in the fact that, in addition to the presence of the multimedia itself and the corresponding software, it is necessary for the teacher to know the methodology for using them and be able to implement this methodology in practice. Teachers and methodologists turned out to be unprepared for the introduction of multimedia technologies in the educational process. The joint use of various types of information presentation (information channels) can significantly not only speed up, but also improve the memorization process. An integrated approach to teaching foreign languages to young learners is being implemented - we can simultaneously teach all types of speech activity in their interconnection.

With the help of multimedia, it is easy to achieve more informative educational material.

The interaction of multimedia teaching software and a computer actually leads to the combination of technical teaching aids with visual aids, and a sharp increase in the teacher's capabilities. First, multimedia can simultaneously stimulate a person's perception and better maintain his attention. Secondly, multimedia teaching software is a cognitive tool of the educational process that enhances the mental abilities of a student of primary classes at the stages of reflection, problem solving and analysis of results. Thirdly, multimedia corresponds to the constructive style of studying disciplines: it stimulates an active position in a person; allows you to re-immers yourself in the events of the lesson and better evaluate them; demonstrates a huge number of information possibilities; reduces the gap between theory and practice, making the latter an integral part of educational programs.

Among other well-known expressive means, multimedia programs are not only universal, but also "self-sufficient", since they can control the effectiveness of the learning process with the help of special subroutines.

In the aspect of language learning by a child of primary classes, multimedia programs support more complex speech skills [139 p. 4]. Children tend to tell themselves why they acted this way and not otherwise, drew just such a picture or chose just such an object on the screen. Multimedia-based classes lead to a higher level of communication and cooperation in children.

The multimedia program is aimed at arousing interest (motivation) in an elementary school student for thematic classes. At the same time, the child can and should work independently with a multimedia program.

As the experiment showed, when explaining new material, the best option for using a multimedia teaching aid is a school class with one or more computers and a video projector, where the role of the teacher remains the leader, and the role of the students is the follower. In the process of training, any of the students can be chosen as the leader in the group, which creates a competitive mood among children. When working with homework, the paradigm "multimedia learning software - student" is fully implemented, and the role of the student becomes completely leading.

The main advantages of multimedia programs are also seen in the variety of examples and their clarity for various learning topics, for example, word order in an English sentence, etc.

Analyzing multimedia systems for teaching a foreign language as an object of research and design, the following should be noted:

1. the education system in this case also belongs to the class of purposeful, if a well-motivated student independently chooses the goals and objectives of education;
2. all elements of the traditional system, being "superimposed" on multimedia, retain their meaning and functions;
3. one learning path for a multimedia system is not enough, because the individual abilities of the students must be taken into account.

Taking this into account, we present the structure of a multimedia system for teaching a foreign language in the diagram. This type of organization of learning corresponds to the paradigm "multimedia learning software - student". Intelligent multimedia capabilities for teaching languages are now concentrated in the software package. The main task that arises when it is created is to ensure flexibility, i.e. ability to meet the needs of users with different abilities.

Working with a multimedia curriculum means the process of forming foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities, in which action initiatives are transferred to the student. In order for these initiatives to be effective, it is necessary to use didactic principles of education in software development, taking into account the individual abilities of a student of primary classes, his consciousness, consistency in work, etc., which is more specifically described above.

The characteristic features of multimedia learning software are:

- 1) the active position of the student (individual choice of the way to comprehend the educational material from among the possible options provided by the development team in the program);
- 2) the transition of the process of cognition from the category of "teach" to a qualitatively new category of "learn" a foreign language independently and consciously;

3) information richness and flexibility of the teaching methodology with multimedia learning software (learning rate control, animation of phenomena, accompanying words with a picture, statistics of questions and answers, load optimization, etc.);

5) "immersion" of the student in the information environment that best motivates him to learn the language.

These features indicate that we are dealing with a new approach to the study of foreign languages, namely, "learner-centered". Therefore, the "multimedia learning software - student" paradigm provides the student with freedom of choice and decision making in the course of the educational process. J. Rubin and I. Thompson consider several possible strategies in this case: "be conscious", "organize your learning", "be creative", "learn to cope with uncertainty", "learn from your mistakes", "use the context".

Thus, the existence of the paradigm "multimedia learning software - student" rests on the following didactic principles:

- the principle of conformity to nature, which states that the technology of teaching a person should be in tune with his biological nature and spiritual needs;
- the principle of activity, which requires great psychological stress from the student: attention, thinking, memory and will;
- the principle of individualization of education, taking into account the individual abilities of students in the course of classes;
- the principle of intensity, which ensures the maximum amount of material assimilation with the minimum training time:
- the principle of visibility;
- the principle of consciousness, which assumes that students understand the tasks of learning.

Summarizing all of the above, we will formulate a number of general requirements for multimedia educational programs for young learners:

1. The student must have direct access to the area of interest.
2. The software must have concise and clear instructions.
3. The software must be able to connect feedback to control learning states.
4. The goals of performing the exercises embedded in the software must be accessible and understandable to the student.

Since the paradigm "multimedia learning software - student" contributes to the independent study of foreign languages, therefore, the student must first of all master the methods of mastering knowledge, namely the methods of teaching. Therefore, from the standpoint of designers, the question arises of how to create such a software product so that it is easy for a student to learn with its help.

I. L. Bim refers to teaching methods [8 p. 2]: familiarization, reflection, training, practice, self-control, rightly believing that they are induced by appropriate teaching methods: demonstration, explanation, organization of training, organization of practice and control over learning. In this case, when designing curricula, various ways of actively supporting teaching methods using sound, image, graphics, text, etc. should be used. (see Table 1 Appendix 2).

Thus, the use of multimedia programs by young learners does not at all exclude traditional teaching methods, but is harmoniously combined with them at all stages of education: familiarization, training, application, control. But the use of multimedia learning software allows

not only to increase the effectiveness of learning many times over, but also to encourage students to further independent study of the English language.

However, the problem of determining the role of multimedia teaching software, its didactic functions is one of the most relevant in the field of methods of multimedia teaching foreign languages to young learners, so it is necessary to determine the functions and tasks of the teacher and multimedia teaching software in the formation of the foundations of foreign language perception. Determination of the list of functions of multimedia learning software in the educational process is directly related to the role it allocates in the educational process. Distinguish between teaching and learning functions. Educational functions are connected with the help of the teacher in the implementation of the educational process. Teaching functions - with learning management through direct interaction with students without the participation of a teacher.

It should be noted the duality of the functions of multimedia learning software, which can be considered both as an activity tool and as an active participant in the educational process. In the first case, multimedia teaching software, first of all, facilitates the work of the teacher. Multimedia technologies are capable of storing large amounts of information, organizing and processing this information, and providing quick access to any part of it. This allows you to improve the accuracy and objectivity of the educational process by systematically recording its parameters and creating a database for each individual student. The teacher thus has the opportunity to adjust his work, choosing the most effective methods and techniques of work.

The main function of multimedia learning software as a tool for the student's activity is to provide support in mastering language and speech material. This saves time and energy for trainees. Students can use a variety of programs (for example, text editors, which are the most widely available general programs that allow the student to enter and edit their own text, as well as design work for printing). Text editors have built-in information systems (spellers, thesauri) that allow you to check spelling, grammar, syntax, select synonyms, use templates for various documents. Working with multimedia learning software in pairs and small groups allows you to increase the level of motivation, since the goal of writing a work for one reader - the teacher - is not stimulating, and when this process becomes a collective creativity, the learning exercise turns into a real communicative task.

Multimedia learning software is also often used for self-study and homework, which contributes to its effective organization and allows you to increase learning time. In addition, multimedia teaching software tolerates student mistakes patiently, ensures confidentiality, cannot be biased towards certain students, which contributes to learning comfort and reduces student anxiety.

The possibilities of multimedia learning software as a teacher in the educational process are assessed differently by researchers. At the present stage of development of multimedia technologies, such an organization of the educational process seems inappropriate, multimedia learning software should not be opposed to the teacher.

Thus, multimedia teaching software cannot replace a teacher, but he can perform certain functions with a high degree of efficiency, allowing the teacher to free up time and energy for the qualitative performance of other functions and intensify the educational process.

One of the most important functions of a teacher is communicative. The human-machine communication system is implemented in the form of a student's interactive interaction with multimedia software tools for teaching and modeling with the help of multimedia technologies the

teacher's activity as a partner in natural speech communication. The purpose of the act of communication is to improve the knowledge, skills and abilities of the student. When implementing the communicative function of the multimedia learning software, they act as the sender of the message. Naturally, the dialogue multimedia learning software - student - multimedia learning software has certain limitations, primarily related to the limitations of the software used. On the other hand, multimedia learning software can effectively act as a communication partner. This is facilitated by the great possibilities of modern multimedia technologies in the field of graphical interface, video and animation. The effect of the student's participation in the events developing in the program is created. Modern programs are even capable of analyzing student audio cues.

Modern multimedia teaching software has ample opportunities in the field of presentation of subject content, which allows you to implement the demonstration function of the teacher. The use of various visual aids, including static (photos, drawings, charts, graphs, tables) and dynamic (video, animation) makes it possible to present the situation in an accessible way, explain the course of action, exclude, where appropriate, the use of the native language. With the help of these means, untranslatable semantization of abstract concepts (for example, "friendship", "love", "punishment", etc.) is possible.

Multimedia learning software has ample opportunities for organizing classes. Multimedia teaching software allows you to diversify the teaching of a foreign language, to change the types of activities, which is especially important for maintaining the interest of children in the classroom. Research activities, games, and any other elements can be organically included in training. Multimedia learning software is used to create authentic, communication-oriented communication situations, it acts as a stimulus for communication. In foreign language classes, individual work of students with programs, pair work and work in small groups is possible. Some researchers prefer pair work, as this involves not only communication between students and multimedia learning software, but also communication between students, they help each other, thus. communication is stimulated. Here it is important to ensure that students use a foreign language, which is often quite difficult, especially when working with children.

The transfer of multimedia software training tools for the management of educational activities allows you to more effectively solve a number of problems. From the point of view of the general theory of management, the teacher must indicate the goals of learning, establish the initial level of students, determine the program of action, provide systematic feedback, process the information coming through the feedback channels, and give a corrective effect. The indication of goals and the definition of the training program remain within the competence of the teacher, while the problem of establishing the initial level of knowledge is successfully solved in autonomous testing multimedia training programs. Multimedia technologies are able to effectively provide feedback and process large amounts of information. Recently, programs have been created characterized by flexible management of educational and cognitive activities and trainees and focus on the development of their creative thinking. Systems are also being developed in which multimedia learning software and the student change places, the computer becomes the object of learning. In this case, the student, programming multimedia actions, independently chooses a learning strategy and independently manages his cognitive activity.

There is no doubt the possibility of transferring to multimedia technologies the controlling - corrective function of a foreign language teacher. The use of multimedia teaching software in

this area allows for ongoing monitoring and final monitoring individually, objectively, there is instant feedback, the teacher's time is freed and the time of the control itself is reduced. Multimedia learning software can correct mistakes, suggest correct answers, and evaluate student progress.

Multimedia is a future-oriented form of learning English. Improving conditions in schools, result in having well-equipped classroom enabling using various forms of multimedia. Currently, there are many students that need motivation in learning and as they are surrounded by multiple stimuli every day, they have to learn in the same way. Teachers need to realize that they need to go away from traditional teaching and use the tools that involve different senses.

REFERENCES

1. Presidential decree No. 5712 of Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 “Xalq ta’limi tizimini 2030-yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to’g’risida” National database of legal documents
2. Верещагина И.Н., Бондаренко К.А., Притыкина Т.А. Английский язык. Учеб. для 2 кл. шк. с углубл. изуч. англ. яз., лицеев, гимназий. 2-й год обучения. В 2 ч. Ч. 2 - М.: Просвещение, 2000. - 128с.
3. Воспитание младшего школьника. // Сост. Л.В. Ковинько, М: 1998. - 245с.
4. Острикова Г. П. Психолингвистика: Курс лекций / [Острикова Галина Николаевна]; М-во образования и науки Рос. Федерации, Рост.гос. экон. унт "РИНХ". - Ростов н/Д.: РГЭУ "РИНХ" 2004. - 131с.
5. Румянцева И. М. Психология речи и лингвопедагогическая психология: новые технологии обучения инстр. яз. Психолингвистика. Лингвопсихология. Лингвопедагогика. Акмеология и онтогенез. Психотерапия в обучении. Интегратив. лингво-психол. тренинг/И.М. Румянцева. - М.: Per Se : Логос, 2004. - 316с.